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THE INFLUENCE OF MOTIVATION AND WORK DISCIPLINE ON APPARATUS PERFORMANCE WITH JOB SATISFACTION AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE (CASE STUDY: THE NORTH TAPANULI POLICE STATION)

ВПЛИВ МОТИВАЦІЇ ТА ТРУДОВОЇ ДИСЦИПЛІНИ НА ЕФЕКТИВНІСТЬ РОБОТИ АПАРАТУ З УРАХУВАННЯМ ЗАДОВОЛЕНОСТІ РОБОТОЮ ЯК ПРОМІЖНОЇ ЗМІННОЇ (НА ПРИКЛАДІ ПОЛІЦЕЙСЬКОГО ВІДДІЛКУ ПІВНІЧНОГО ТАПАНУЛІ)

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Діан Фітрі Амбаріта, Алекс Трібуана Сутанто, Кат Фітрі Ростіна, Пурнама Янті Пурба. Вплив мотивації та трудової дисципліни на ефективність роботи апарату з урахуванням задоволеності роботою як проміжної змінної (на прикладі поліцейського відділку Північного Тапанулі). Науково-методична стаття.

Це дослідження розглядає, як мотивація до роботи та дисципліна впливають на ефективність роботи поліцейських у поліцейському відділку Північного Тапанулі, враховуючи задоволеність роботою як проміжну змінну. Вибірка включає 71 респондента, відібраного за допомогою неімовірнісної вибірки. Дані були зібрані за допомогою анкет, спостережень, документації, оглядів літератури та онлайн-джерел, а також проаналізовані за допомогою SPSS 23 з використанням статистичних тестів, таких як t-тести та аналіз шляхів. Результати показують, що мотивація та дисципліна позитивно та суттєво впливають як на задоволеність роботою, так і на продуктивність. Задоволеність роботою також позитивно впливає на продуктивність, що свідчить про те, що покращення мотивації та дисципліни може підвищити задоволеність, продуктивність та загальну ефективність роботи відділу.

Ключові слова: мотивація до роботи, дисципліна, продуктивність, задоволеність роботою, поліцейські, Північний Тапанулі

Dian Fitri Ambarita, Alex Tribuana Sutanto, Cut Fitri Rostina, Purnama Yanti Purba. The Influence of Motivation and Work Discipline on Apparatus Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable (Case Study: The North Tapanuli Police Station). Scientific and methodical article.

This study examines how work motivation and discipline influence the performance of police officers at the North Tapanuli Police Department, with job satisfaction as an intervening variable. The sample includes 71 respondents selected through non-probability sampling. Data were collected using questionnaires, observations, documentation, literature reviews, and online sources, and analyzed with SPSS 23 using statistical tests such as t-tests and path analysis. Results show that motivation and discipline positively and significantly affect both job satisfaction and performance. Job satisfaction also positively impacts performance, indicating that improving motivation and discipline can enhance satisfaction, performance, and overall departmental effectiveness.

Keywords: work motivation, discipline, performance, job satisfaction, police officers, North Tapanuli

Competition in the era of globalization is getting tighter every day, therefore human resources are very important to maintain the good name of government agencies in order to survive and be able to get good results of course. In order to achieve the success and survival of an organization, in this case, a leader must be wise in maintaining and improving his resources, including in improving the performance of the apparatus. According to Article 4 Number 2 of 2002 concerning the Indonesian National Police, it is stated that the Police is an institution that carries out the task of realizing domestic security, including the maintenance of public security and order, order and law enforcement, the implementation of protection, protection, and services to the community, as well as the fostering of public peace by upholding human rights.

Analysis of recent research and publications

To get satisfactory results, this agency really needs apparatus who have professional performance to achieve organizational targets and goals. This condition requires Polres Tapanuli Utara to implement a strategy to improve the quality of human resources. Polres Tapanuli Utara realizes that to maximize the performance of the apparatus, the agency must implement a motivation system, and good work discipline so that the agency can maximize good and quality human resources. With the existence of Polres

in North Tapanuli, it will facilitate human activities in taking care of something related to this, for example; taking care of driving licenses (SIM), SKCK, and can also communicate and exchange information. The North Tapanuli District Police is based on Jalan Suprpto No.2 Hutatoruan X, Kec. Tarutung, Kab. North Tapanuli, North Sumatra. Performance is the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him (A.A. Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara, 2017: 67). Job results are the results obtained by a person in doing work according to job requirements or performance standards. There are two elements contained in performance appraisal, namely the achievement of work results and work standards, where to determine the performance of the two elements are compared. Various measures of performance include the amount of work, quality of

work, timeliness, attendance and ability to work together.

Based on the researcher's interview with several apparatus at North Tapanuli Police Station regarding motivation, and work discipline through job satisfaction, information was obtained that the existing work motivation at the agency had been established. The results of the interview at the North Tapanuli Police Station indicate that there are problems that indicate the presence of absenteeism / tardiness of the apparatus. This can be seen from the tardiness of an apparatus, but the good news is that the number of tardiness is getting smaller. Based on the results of observations, researchers found several apparatus who were late every month. This is evidenced by the data on the tardiness of the work of the apparatus at the North Tapanuli Police during October 2023 to February 2024. The tardiness data can be seen as follows.

Table 1. Apparatus Work Delay Data Polres Tapanuli Utara Period October 2023 to February 2024

Month	Year	Total		Percentage		Description
		Present	Absent	Present	Absent	
1. October	2023	247	4	99.984	0.016	100%
2. November	2023	247	4	99.984	0.016	100%
3. December	2023	247	3	99.988	0.012	100%
4. January	2024	247	1	99.996	0.004	100%
5. February	2024	247	1	99.996	0.004	100%
Total				99.888%	0.112%	100%

Source: compiled by authors on materials [1]

Based on the data obtained and the results of observations at the North Tapanuli Police Station, the author conducted further interviews with several

apparatus working at the North Tapanuli Police Station. The interview was conducted to find out what factors affect the performance of the apparatus.

Table 2. Pre-Survey Data on Factors Affecting Apparatus Performance North Tapanuli District Police

Factors Affecting Civil Servant Performance	Number	Percentage
Motivation	8	36.36%
Work discipline	5	22.72%
Job satisfaction	9	40.90%
Number	22	100%

Source: authors' own elaboration

In the table above, the North Tapanuli Polres company has factors that affect the performance of its apparatus, seen from motivation has a percentage of 36.36%, work discipline has a percentage of 22.72%, and job satisfaction has a percentage of 40.90%. This means that the average apparatus at North Tapanuli Police Station understands how to improve apparatus performance.

The main part

From the results of the initial interview, it can be seen that many of the apparatus mentioned job satisfaction and followed by motivation and work discipline that affect apparatus performance. So that researchers feel interested in examining the variables of motivation, work discipline, job satisfaction, and performance at the North Tapanuli Police Station. So based on the explanation and background description above, the researcher wishes to conduct research with

the title "The Effect of Motivation and Work Discipline on Apparatus Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at North Tapanuli Police Station".

2. Object and subject of research.

The object of this research is the performance of the apparatus in the North Tapanuli Resort Police (Polres). This research focuses on how work motivation and work discipline affect apparatus performance, with job satisfaction as an intervening variable. The performance of the apparatus is measured based on the work results achieved in carrying out their duties and responsibilities, which include effectiveness and efficiency in carrying out police duties. The subjects of this study were police officers at the North Tapanuli Police Station. The total research subjects amounted to 71 people, who were selected using non-probability sampling method. These apparatuses consist of various levels and divisions within the Polres, who are responsible for operational, administrative, and public

service tasks. Apparatuses at Polres Tapanuli Utara are expected to have a high level of professionalism in carrying out their duties, in accordance with established regulations and standards. However, there are several operational challenges that affect their performance, such as varying levels of motivation and work discipline. This study identifies these issues to understand the factors that affect apparatus performance and how improving motivation and work discipline can improve their satisfaction and performance.

3. Target of research.

The main purpose of this research is to analyze and understand the effect of work motivation and work discipline on the performance of the North Tapanuli Police apparatus, with job satisfaction as an intervening variable. This study aims to:

1. Identifying the Effect of Work Motivation: Understand the extent to which work motivation can improve the performance of the apparatus at North Tapanuli Police Station, as well as how motivation affects the job satisfaction of the apparatus.

2. Identifying the Influence of Work Discipline: Knowing the effect of work discipline on apparatus performance. Work discipline here is seen as the apparatus' compliance with the rules and procedures that apply at the North Tapanuli Police Station.

3. Analyzing Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable: Investigating the role of job satisfaction as a variable that mediates the relationship between work motivation and work discipline with apparatus performance. This research seeks to understand whether job satisfaction strengthens or weakens the relationship between these variables.

4. Improving Apparatus Performance: Identifying steps that Polres Tapanuli Utara can take to improve apparatus motivation, discipline and job satisfaction in order to improve overall performance.

By achieving these targets, this research is expected to provide deeper insights into the factors that influence apparatus performance, thus assisting Polres Tapanuli Utara in designing strategies to improve organizational effectiveness and efficiency.

4. Literature analysis.

1. Work Motivation.

Work motivation is an internal drive that moves the apparatus to achieve work goals. According to Winardi (2016), motivation is a potential force in humans that can be developed or influenced by external factors, such as rewards or awards. This motivation is considered an important factor affecting performance, because motivated individuals tend to show higher levels of engagement and productivity in their work (Robbins, 2018).

2. Work Discipline.

Work discipline refers to the attitude of a person's willingness and willingness to comply with the norms and rules that apply in the organization (Sutrisno, 2010). Good work discipline is expected to encourage employees to work more efficiently and effectively, which ultimately improves overall organizational performance. Handoko (2008) emphasizes that

discipline is a key element in maintaining operational stability and achieving organizational goals.

3. Job Satisfaction.

Job satisfaction is the level of emotional comfort felt by employees towards their jobs, which includes perceptions of the work environment, coworkers, and rewards (Robbins, 2018). Previous research shows that job satisfaction has an important role as a mediator between motivational factors and performance (Greenberg & Baron, 2000). Employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to have higher morale and are less likely to be absent or leave work (Kreitner & Kinicki, 2014).

4. Apparatus Performance.

Apparatus performance is defined as the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given (Mangkunegara, 2017). This performance can be influenced by various factors, including work motivation, discipline, and job satisfaction. According to Wirawan (2012), good performance is the result of a harmonious interaction between individual abilities and motivational factors.

Relationship between Variables: Various studies have shown that work motivation and discipline have a significant direct influence on apparatus performance. The study by Syaifuddin (2012) shows that high motivation and good discipline can improve positive organizational culture and affect performance. In addition, research by Wijayanti Saputri (2019) indicated that job satisfaction acts as a mediator in the relationship between motivation, discipline, and performance, indicating that job satisfaction can strengthen the positive effects of motivation and discipline on employee performance.

5. Research methods.

Research Design: This study uses a quantitative research design with descriptive and causal approaches. The descriptive approach is used to provide an overview of the research variables, such as work motivation, work discipline, job satisfaction, and officer performance. The causal approach is used to analyze the cause-and-effect relationships between these variables.

Population and Sample: The population of this study includes all police officers at the North Tapanuli Police Department, totaling 247 individuals. The sample was selected using a non-probability sampling method, specifically purposive sampling, where 71 respondents were chosen based on specific criteria, such as employment status and tasks relevant to this study.

Data Collection Techniques: Data for this study were collected using several techniques: Questionnaires: The primary data collection tool was a closed-ended questionnaire designed to measure the variables of work motivation, work discipline, job satisfaction, and officer performance. The questionnaire was constructed using a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5, where respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with various statements presented. Observation: Direct observations were conducted to understand the work context and

behavior of officers at the North Tapanuli Police Department, aiming to support the quantitative data obtained from the questionnaires. Documentation Study: Relevant documents related to officer performance, such as attendance reports and performance evaluations, were collected to provide additional information and strengthen the research findings. Literature Review: Previous literature and studies relevant to this topic were reviewed to provide theoretical and contextual foundations for the research.

Data Analysis Techniques: The collected data were analyzed using SPSS software version 23. Several analytical techniques were used, including: Instrument Testing: Validity and reliability tests were conducted to ensure that the data collection instrument (questionnaire) had adequate accuracy and consistency. Normality Test: This test was conducted to check the data distribution to meet the normality assumptions required for further statistical analysis. Multicollinearity Test: This test was conducted to ensure no strong correlations between the independent variables that could cause problems in regression analysis. Heteroscedasticity Test: This test was used to examine whether the variables had consistent variability across the data range, ensuring that the homoscedasticity assumption was not violated. t-Test (Partial Test): This test was used to assess the significance of the influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable. Coefficient of

Determination (R^2): This measure was used to determine how much the independent variables could explain the variance in the dependent variable. Path Analysis: This technique was used to test the causal model involving the intervening variable, job satisfaction, in the relationship between work motivation and discipline and officer performance. Research Procedure: The research was conducted in several stages as follows: Research Preparation: Determining the topic, formulating the problem, defining research objectives, and developing research instruments. Data Collection: Conducting data collection through questionnaires, observation, documentation studies, and literature review. Data Processing and Analysis: The collected data were analyzed using SPSS version 23 with the analytical techniques described above. Reporting the Research Results: Preparing the research report based on the data analysis and interpretation performed. Using these research methods, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the influence of work motivation and discipline on officer performance, as well as the role of job satisfaction as an intervening variable at the North Tapanuli Police Department.

6. Research results.

In table 3 below, the partial influence of motivation and work discipline variables on commitment will be explained.

Table 3. t Test Results (Partial)

Model		Coefficients ^a			t	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.582	4.308		1.064	.291
	Motivation (X1)	.439	.150	.296	2.919	.005
	Work Discipline (X2)	1.478	.290	.515	5.090	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja (Y)

Source: authors' own elaboration

Motivation: t-value = 2.919 t-table value = 1.995 Sig t = 0.005 The t-value (2.919) is greater than the t-table value (1.995), and the significance level (Sig t) for the motivation variable is 0.005, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, motivation has a significant partial effect on performance. Work Discipline: t-value = 5.090 t-table value = 1.995 Sig t = 0.000 The t-value (5.090) is greater than the t-table value (1.995), and the significance level (Sig t) for the work discipline

variable is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, work discipline also has a significant partial effect on performance. In summary, both motivation and work discipline have a significant partial impact on performance.

In table 4 below, the partial influence of motivation and work discipline variables on job satisfaction will be explained.

Table 4. t Test Results (Partial).

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.747	1.837		2.583	.012
	Motivation (X1)	.571	.064	.581	8.906	.000
	Work Discipline (X2)	.813	.124	.428	6.562	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Kerja (Z)

Source: authors' own elaboration

Based on the calculations presented in Table 4, the results can be explained as follows: Motivation: t-value = 8.906 t-table value = 1.995 Sig t = 0.000 The t-value (8.906) is greater than the t-table value (1.995), and the significance level (Sig t) for the motivation variable is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, motivation has a significant partial effect on job satisfaction. Work Discipline: t-value = 6.562 t-table value = 1.995 Sig t = 0.000 The t-value (6.562) is greater than the t-table

value (1.995), and the significance level (Sig t) for the work discipline variable is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, work discipline also has a significant partial effect on job satisfaction. In summary, both motivation and work discipline have a significant partial impact on job satisfaction.

In table 5 below, the partial influence of the job satisfaction variable on performance will be explained.

Table 5. t Test Results (Partial)

Model		Coefficients ^a			T	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.320	3.324		-.397	.693
	Kepuasan Kerja (Z)	1.273	.098	.842	12.982	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja (Y)

Source: authors' own elaboration

Based on the calculations presented in Table 6, the results can be explained as follows: Job Satisfaction: t-value = 12.982 t-table value = 1.995 Sig t = 0.000 The t-value (12.982) is greater than the t-table value (1.995), and the significance level (Sig t) for the job satisfaction variable is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, job satisfaction has a significant partial effect on performance.

This section describes each path in the model using path analysis. Each path tested shows the direct and indirect effects of motivation and work discipline on performance through job satisfaction. Determining whether each path is significant will indicate whether the proposed hypotheses are accepted or rejected. Each path tested represents a hypothesis in this study. The path coefficients can be seen in Table 6 below.

Tabel 6. Analisis Jalur

Dependent Variables	Dependent Variables	Beta (β)	t-tabel	p-value	Description
1. Motivation	Performance	0.296	2.919	0.005	Significant
2. Work Discipline	Performance	0.515	5.090	0.000	Significant
3. Motivation	Job Satisfaction	0.581	8.906	0.000	Significant
4. Work Discipline	Job Satisfaction	0.428	6.562	0.000	Significant
5. Job Satisfaction	Performance	0.842	12.982	0.000	Significant

Source: authors' own elaboration

a. Effect of Motivation (X1) on Performance (Y).

Based on Table 6, it can be seen that for testing the motivation variable on performance, the beta (β) value is 0.296 with a p-value of 0.005. Because the p-value is smaller than α (0.005 < 0.05), H0 is rejected. This there is a significant effect of motivation on performance.

b. Effect of Work Discipline (X2) on Performance (Y).

Based on Table 6, it can be seen that for testing the work discipline variable on performance, the beta (β) value is 0.515 with a p-value of 0.000. Because the p-value is smaller than α (0.000 < 0.05), H0 is rejected. This there is a significant effect of work discipline on performance.

c. The Effect of Motivation (X1) on Job Satisfaction (Z).

Based on Table 6, it can be seen that for testing the motivation variable on job satisfaction, the beta (β) value is 0.581 with a p-value of 0.000. Because the p-value is smaller than α (0.000 < 0.05), H0 is rejected. This there is a significant effect of motivation on job satisfaction.

d. The Effect of Work Discipline (X2) on Job Satisfaction (Z).

Based on Table 6, it can be seen that for testing the work discipline variable on job satisfaction, the beta (β) value is 0.428 with a p-value of 0.000. Because the p-value is greater than α (0.000 < 0.05), H0 is rejected. This there is a significant effect of work discipline on job satisfaction.

e. Effect of Job Satisfaction (Z) on Performance (Y).

Based on Table 6, it can be seen that for testing the job satisfaction variable on performance, the beta (β) value is 0.842 with a p-value of 0.000. Because the p-value is smaller than α (0.000 < 0.05), H0 is rejected. This there is a significant effect of job satisfaction on performance.

7. Prospects for further research development.

Based on the above conclusions, the researchers formulated the following research suggestion, It is expected for future research to expand research with similar themes so as to obtain better findings in explaining the factors that affect performance in Indonesia.

Conclusion

1. Motivation has a positive and significant influence on the performance of the apparatus at the North Tapanuli Police. This means that if motivation is strong, performance will also increase.

2. Work discipline has a positive and significant influence on the performance of the apparatus at the North Tapanuli Police Station. This means that if work discipline is strong then performance will also increase.

3. Motivation has a positive and significant influence on apparatus job satisfaction at the North Tapanuli Police Station. This means that if motivation is strong, job satisfaction will also increase.

4. Work discipline has a positive and significant influence on the job satisfaction of the apparatus at the

North Tapanuli Police Station. This means that if work discipline is strong, job satisfaction will also increase.

5. Motivation has a positive and significant influence on performance through apparatus job satisfaction at the North Tapanuli Police. This means that if motivation is strong, performance will also increase supported by job satisfaction.

6. Work discipline has a positive and significant influence on performance through apparatus job satisfaction at the North Tapanuli Police. This means that if work discipline is strong, performance will also increase supported by job satisfaction.

Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on performance at the North Tapanuli Police Station. This means that if job satisfaction is strong then performance will also increase.

Abstract

This study explores in depth the relationship between work motivation, discipline, job satisfaction, and employee performance among police officers at the North Tapanuli Police Department. Specifically, it aims to determine how motivation and discipline contribute to overall job performance, while also examining the mediating role of job satisfaction. The research sample includes 71 respondents selected using a non-probability sampling technique to ensure representation of various ranks and divisions within the department.

Data were collected through multiple methods – questionnaires, observations, documentation studies, literature reviews, and internet sources – to ensure comprehensive coverage of both quantitative and qualitative aspects. The collected data were analyzed using SPSS version 23, employing a series of statistical tests such as instrument reliability and validity tests, normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity tests, followed by t-tests, coefficient of determination (R^2), and path analysis to assess direct and indirect relationships among variables.

The results show that work motivation and discipline have a positive and statistically significant influence on the performance of police officers. Officers with higher motivation and stronger work discipline tend to demonstrate greater responsibility, efficiency, and commitment to organizational goals. Moreover, both motivation and discipline significantly affect job satisfaction, which in turn acts as a crucial mediating factor enhancing performance outcomes.

The findings underscore that fostering intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, establishing clear rules and standards, and promoting a disciplined work environment can substantially improve both job satisfaction and operational performance. These improvements ultimately contribute to the organizational effectiveness of the North Tapanuli Police Department. The study highlights the importance of human resource management strategies that focus on motivation and discipline as key drivers for sustainable performance improvement in public sector organizations.

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